

The Impact of Customer Relationship Management on OTT TV Platform Purchase Intention: The Role of Positive Word-of-Mouth and Brand Trust

Correspond author: PhD Student Aziz KÖROĞLU

University of Hull, Hull / United Kingdom.

ORCID: 0009-0005-9849-6431

Independent Researcher Mehmet TEMİR

Tokat / Türkiye

ORCID: 0000-0001-7259-335X

Abstract

The rapid development of Over-the-Top Television (OTT TV) platforms has increased competition in the digital broadcasting sector and highlighted the importance of customer relationship management and consumer-based relational factors. The aim of this study is to examine the relationships between customer relationship management (CRM), positive word-of-mouth (WOM), brand trust, and purchase intention in relation to OTT TV platforms. The study also evaluated the mediating roles of positive WOM and brand trust. The study sample consisted of 557 participants living in Sakarya and subscribed to at least one OTT TV platform. Convenience sampling was used as the sample selection method. Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used in the analysis of the data. The analyses revealed that CRM positively influences positive WOM and brand trust; positive WOM positively influences brand trust and purchase intention; and brand trust positively influences purchase intention. Furthermore, positive WOM mediates the relationship between CRM and brand trust, while brand trust mediates the relationship between positive WOM and purchase intention. This study contributes to the literature by explaining consumer behavior towards OTT TV platforms using a holistic model based on relational and trust-based factors. In addition, the research provides OTT platform managers with important insights into developing trust-based marketing strategies, promoting positive WOM, and strengthening customer relationships.

Keywords: Customer relationships management, brand trust, positive WOM, OTT TV platforms, digital platforms

1. Introduction

Today, with digitalization, media consumption habits have changed, and traditional broadcasting is being replaced by internet-based digital broadcasting. Digital streaming platforms, particularly those known as OTT TV, have created a new area of competition within the media industry by enabling users to consume content regardless of time and location. The rapid rise of platforms like Netflix, Disney+, Amazon Prime Video, and HBO Max has made it necessary to examine more closely the factors influencing consumer purchasing intent. In the

highly competitive digital TV platform market, businesses strive to differentiate themselves not only through content quality but also through the relationships they build with consumers, their ability to establish brand trust, and the positive feedback users give about their platform.

In this context, CRM is considered a critical element in enabling businesses to develop long-term and sustainable relationships with consumers. The CRM approach aims to improve business performance by understanding customer needs, providing personalized service, and increasing customer satisfaction (Payne & Frow, 2005). The ability to continuously analyze user behavior on digital platforms allows for more effective use of CRM applications. Especially on OTT TV platforms, analyzing user preferences, providing personalized content recommendations, and improving user experience play a significant role in increasing customer loyalty and purchase intent (Chen & Popovich, 2003). The literature indicates that CRM applications have positive effects on customer satisfaction, loyalty, and repeat purchase behavior (Sin et al., 2005).

One of the effects of customer relationship management is word-of-mouth (WOM) communication among consumers about a business. WOM is defined as consumers sharing their experiences with products or services with other individuals (Arndt, 1967). With digitalization, the concept of WOM has moved to the online environment and can reach much wider audiences through social media and digital platforms. Positive WOM, in particular, is considered an important communication tool that strengthens consumers' brand perception and increases their purchase intention (Cheung & Thadani, 2012). In the context of OTT TV platforms, positive user reviews regarding content quality, ease of use, and platform experience can influence potential users' attitudes towards the platform. This is because consumers place greater importance on the experiences of other users, especially in intangible and experience-based services (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004).

For positive WOM to be effective, consumers need to trust the brand. Brand trust is defined as consumers' belief that a brand will fulfill its promises (Delgado-Ballester, 2004). In the service sector, trust can directly influence consumers' purchasing decisions by reducing uncertainty and perceived risk. On OTT TV platforms, users' expectations regarding personal data sharing, subscription systems, and content quality further increase the importance of brand trust. Building trust encourages users to engage with the platform long-term and purchase paid subscriptions. Brand trust is also considered an important psychological mechanism that strengthens the impact of positive WOM on purchase intention (Morgan & Hunt, 1994).

Purchase intention is defined as a consumer's conscious plan to buy a particular product or service (Ajzen, 1991). Purchase intention for technology-based services is influenced by various factors, including perceived benefit, user experience, trust, and social impact. In the context of OTT TV platforms, it is considered that social communication processes and consumer relations, in addition to technical features, are important in forming purchase intention for a platform. Therefore, examining the relationships between CRM, positive WOM, brand trust, and purchase intention is important both theoretically and practically.

Although there are studies in the literature that examine the relationships between these variables, studies that examine these relationships within the context of OTT TV platforms appear to be limited. Especially in today's rapidly growing digital streaming platforms, examining the relational and psychological factors influencing users' subscription decisions within a holistic model framework constitutes a significant research gap. Accordingly, this

study aims to examine the effects of customer relationship management on positive WOM and brand trust, and how these variables are reflected in OTT TV platform purchase intention. The research is expected to contribute to the digital media marketing literature and also offer important insights to OTT TV platform managers regarding the development of consumer relationship strategies.

2. Literature review

2.1. The relationship between CRM and positive WOM

Today, OTT platforms are strengthening CRM functions at the heart of the interaction between users and content providers, and increasing their capacity to personalize the user experience. In this context, it is argued that the relationship established between customer relationship management (CRM) and OTT users plays a role in triggering positive communication WOM/eWOM. In particular, the impact of content quality, ease of use, and expectation-confirmation processes on user satisfaction increases users' commitment to the platform and, consequently, their positive WOM/eWOM intentions (Naidoo, 2023; Saggu & Mohan, 2024). In OTT platforms, quality factors and meeting expectations are key elements that significantly increase user satisfaction. This is supported by findings that it strengthens both continuance intention and positive WOM intention (Saggu & Mohan, 2024). Within the scope of CRM, strengthening social media strategy and customer engagement is a crucial mechanism for triggering positive WOM. Increased interaction through social media accelerates the flow of positive WOM communication, which strengthens potential users' trust in and intention to use the platform (Rukmana et al., 2024). By synthesizing the findings in this literature, the following hypothesis has been developed:

H₁. CRM on OTT TV platforms positively effects positive WOM.

2.2. The relationship between CRM and brand trust

As OTT TV platforms strengthen their CRM applications, brand trust among users is expected to increase, and this trust is expected to positively impact purchasing/subscription decisions. CRM's ability to offer user-specific content recommendations, fast and effective customer support, and trust-based communication strengthens brand trust (Kour & Chhabria, 2022). CRM's trust-related outcomes provide important indicators in terms of brand image, perceived reliability, and sustainable customer relationships. These elements are considered among the key determinants of brand trust in the context of OTT platforms (Amoroso et al., 2021; Kour & Chhabria, 2022). The quality and trust-oriented structure of CRM applications improves user experience, while factors such as ease of use of the website or application, secure payment systems, and quick problem resolution increase users' trust in the platform, contributing to the formation of brand trust (Kour & Chhabria, 2022). In addition, it is stated that multi-dimensional elements shaping the OTT experience, such as user experience, personalization, content quality, and accessibility, are also effective in the development of brand trust. Accordingly, personalized services and reliable customer support offered by CRM strengthen consumers' perception of trust (Alam et al., 2021; Nandya & Permana, 2021; Priya & Thowseaf, 2025). In line with these findings in the literature, the following hypothesis has been developed:

H₂. CRM on OTT TV platforms positively impacts brand trust.

2.3. The relationship between positive WOM and brand trust

As positive word-of-mouth (WOM) increases for OTT TV platforms, brand trust is also positively affected. Increased user trust in the platform through positive reviews and recommendations strengthens their intention to renew subscriptions and recommend the platform to others (Batra, 2016; Çadırcı et al., 2022). The impact of positive WOM on trust, brand image, and purchasing behavior in the digital environment forms a powerful mechanism in interaction with OTT experience and CRM applications. Secure communication, transparent information sharing, and secure transaction processes are among the key determinants of this relationship (Kour & Chhabria, 2022; Siriwardana & Ismail, 2020). Factors such as content quality, user experience, and platform security trigger the formation of positive WOM, strengthening brand trust; this, in turn, increases user trust in the platform and supports their intention to recommend it (Ataizi & Sever, 2016). Furthermore, elements related to the OTT experience, such as user experience, content variety, and personalization, along with the trust-focused outputs of CRM, strengthen the formation and sustainability of brand trust. In this context, trust and positive word-of-mouth mutually reinforce each other (Çadırcı et al., 2022; Islam & Rahman, 2016). By synthesizing the findings in this literature, the following hypothesis has been developed:

H3. Positive WOM towards OTT TV platforms positively impacts brand trust.

2.4. The relationship between positive WOM and purchase intention

The increasing importance of OTT TV platforms in video media services has critically increased the impact of user-to-user communication on purchasing decisions. In addition to traditional WOM, electronic WOM also influences subscription intentions and purchasing behavior through content quality, trust, and user satisfaction. The findings support the idea that peer-to-peer recommendations on OTT TV platforms play a critical role in building trust and influencing subscription decisions (Arcos et al., 2014; Gupta, 2023; Osorio Andrade et al., 2023; Steffany et al., 2022). In this context, the hypothesis that positive WOM communication increases purchase intention for OTT TV platforms is consistently supported by findings in the global literature (Arroyo & Sanchez, 2024; Gomez & Perez, 2020; Gupta, 2023; Jaime et al., 2022; Steffany et al., 2022). By synthesizing the findings in this literature, the following hypothesis has been developed:

H4. Positive WOM towards OTT TV platforms positively influences purchase intention.

2.5. The relationship between brand trust and purchase intention

Brand trust has been found to strengthen consumer confidence in the OTT TV platform, thereby increasing their intention to purchase subscription/paid content directly. This effect has been reported in numerous studies, where trust acts as a direct trigger for customers' positive attitudes and preferences towards the platform. In the OTT TV context, trust creates a perception of security, reference, and reliability that accelerates users' content consumption and subscription decisions; in this context, a direct impact pathway stands out. In particular, trust appears to support rapid decision-making and directly trigger subscription/payment intentions (Habib et al., 2022; Priya & Thowseaf, 2025; Soren & Chakraborty, 2025; Steffany et al., 2022). By synthesizing the findings in this literature, the following hypothesis has been developed:

H5. Brand trust in OTT TV platforms positively influences purchase intention.

2.6. The mediating role of positive WOM

Today, CRM applications improve the quality and continuity of interactions with customers; in this context, communications carried out through social media and digital communication channels play a critical role in building brand trust (Wongsansukcharoen, 2022). Positive electronic WOM and real-world interactions, in particular, stand out as dynamics that can strengthen consumer perceptions and indirectly influence brand trust (Maya et al., 2021; Putri & Fauzi, 2023; Tafolli et al., 2025). Some studies report that positive WOM affects brand trust, and this effect is reinforced by CRM influencing WOM (Tuzcu, 2025). Customers with high CRM activity are more likely to share positive experiences through e-WOM (Rehman et al., 2020; Dao et al., 2025). This positive e-WOM indirectly supports the strengthening of brand trust. Increasing customer WOM behavior through CRM applications strengthens consumers' perception of trust (Tuzcu, 2025; Rastini & Nurcaya, 2019). E-WOM is an important communication mechanism that conveys consumer experiences to a wide audience on online platforms and triggers the formation of brand trust (Sari et al., 2021; Seo & Park, 2018). The effectiveness of this mechanism depends on how CRM shapes the customer experience; because CRM facilitates the production of positive e-WOM by offering personalized interactions, quick responses, and trust signals to the customer (Mohammed, 2024; Rastini & Nurcaya, 2019). This idea forms the basis of CRM's indirect impact on brand trust. By synthesizing the findings in this literature, the following hypothesis has been developed:

H₆. OTT TV platform customer relationship management has an indirect positive impact on brand trust through positive WOM.

2.7. The mediating role of brand trust

There is strong evidence that trust is converted into or indirectly strengthened by attitudes influenced by e-WOM (Steffany et al., 2022). WOM plays a fundamental role in consumer decision-making processes and influences purchase intention in conjunction with brand trust. Many studies have shown that e-WOM has a direct impact on purchase intention; however, mediating variables such as brand trust indirectly strengthen this effect (Idriana et al., 2022; Ali & Javed, 2023; Dwilestari & Erdiansyah, 2023; Khan & Bhutto, 2023; Qadri et al., 2023; Sirojuddin et al., 2024). In this context, it is argued that positive WOM messages strengthen brand trust and consequently increase purchase intention (Ali & Javed, 2023; Firman et al., 2021; Kamalaseana & Sirisena, 2021). Therefore, it is possible to establish a model in which brand trust mediates purchase intention as an indirect mechanism. The indirect effect of brand trust on purchase intention is an incentive mechanism because trust reduces consumer risk, increases brand loyalty and perceived value, thus reinforcing positive mediating effects (Bernarto et al., 2020; Liao, 2015; Lu et al., 2024; Mvondo et al., 2022). Many studies in the literature focusing on models where e-WOM and brand trust work together show that brand trust plays a mediating role in the relationship with e-WOM. In particular, it has been shown that e-WOM indirectly influences purchase intention and that this influence is strengthened through brand trust (Idriana et al., 2022; Ali & Javed, 2023; Qadri et al., 2023). By synthesizing the findings in this literature, the following hypothesis has been developed:

H₇. Positive WOM towards OTT TV platforms has an indirect positive impact on purchase intention through brand trust.

2.8. Conceptual model

The literature on customer relationship management, positive WOM, and brand trust, and their total and indirect effects on purchase intention, has led us to conclude that positive WOM and brand trust may play a mediating role in the relationships between these variables. Based on this the research model is developed in Figure 1 to test this effect empirically.

Figure 1. Research model

3. Methodology

3.1. Survey questionnaire design

The survey form consists of two sections. The first section includes questions designed to determine participants' gender, age, education level, monthly income, and the digital TV platform they subscribe to. The second section includes items related to CRM, positive WOM, brand trust, and determining purchase intention. To measure perceptions of customer relationship management activities, the Customer Relationship Management Scale, consisting of five items and taken from Dastane's (2020) study, was used. To measure positive WOM, the four-item WOM scale developed by Gremler and Gwinner (2000) was used. To measure brand trust, a four-item scale taken from Delgado-Ballester's (2004) study was used. To measure purchase intention, a four-item scale developed by Yoo and Donthu (2001) was used. All scales are prepared using a 5-point Likert type.

3.2. Data collection and sampling

The study sample consisted of participants living in Sakarya and subscribed to OTT TV platforms. Convenience sampling was used to determine the sample. Data was collected between October 25, 2025 and November 10, 2025 by three pollsters on the busiest street in Sakarya. The survey form was administered to participants in person. All 557 survey forms

collected were included in the analysis. A sample size of 384 data obtained from a population of one million people is considered sufficient (Yazıcıoğlu & Erdoğan, 2004). The total population of Sakarya province is approximately one million. Therefore, the sample size of the study is sufficient.

3.3. Reliability of the questionnaire

The reliability of the scales was analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. The results show that the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient for the CRM scale is 0.740; the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient for the positive WOM scale is 0.952; the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient for the brand trust scale is 0.908; and the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient for the purchase intention scale is 0.883. Since these values are above 0.70, it was concluded that the scales are reliable and consistent for subsequent processing (Büyüköztürk, 2020).

4. Results analysis

4.1. Respondents' profile

Participants' gender, age, education level, monthly household income, and subscribed digital TV platform are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic information of respondents

Items	Categories	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	274	49,2
	Female	283	50,8
Age	18-27	114	20,5
	28-37	138	24,8
	38-47	140	25,1
	48-57	99	17,8
	≥58	66	11,8
Education	Primary/Middle School	78	14,0
	High School	150	26,9
	Associate Degree	107	19,2
	Bachelor's Degree	150	26,9
	Postgraduate Degree	72	12,9
Household Income	≤22.105 TL	70	12,6
	22.106 TL-44.000 TL	156	28,0
	44.001 TL-66.000 TL	140	25,1
	66.001 TL-88.000 TL	109	19,6
	≥88.001 TL	82	14,7
OTT TV	HBO Max	150	26,9
	Netflix	125	22,4
	Prime Video	114	20,5
	Disney	100	18,0
	Others	68	12,2
	Total	557	100

4.2. Convergent validity

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted to test the structural validity of the scales. A theoretically significant modification was made between the error terms to improve model fit. The CFA results showed factor loadings ranging from 0.459 to 0.976. Furthermore, composite reliability (CR) values were above 0.70, and average variance extracted (AVE) values were above 0.50 (Hair et al., 2014). These results indicate that the scales have achieved convergent validity. Therefore, this model meets the convergent validity criteria, which are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of confirmatory factor analysis

Items	Significant test of parameter estimation				Item Reliability		Composite Reliability	Convergence Validity	
	Unstd	S.E.	C.R.	p	Factor Loading	SMC	CR	AVE	
Customer Relationship Management	Crm1	1.000			0.459	0.211	0.873	0.600	
	Crm2	0.864	0.083	12.267	0.000	0.489			0.239
	Crm3	2.181	0.188	11.627	0.000	0.941			0.885
	Crm4	2.087	0.180	11.580	0.000	0.926			0.857
	Crm5	1.890	0.165	11.482	0.000	0.899			0.807
Positive WOM	Wom1	1.000			0.873	0.761	0.953	0.835	
	Wom2	1.028	0.032	32.569	0.000	0.921			0.847
	Wom3	1.004	0.031	32.233	0.000	0.916			0.840
	Wom4	1.047	0.030	34.592	0.000	0.945			0.893
Brand Trust	Bt1	1.000			0.893	0.797	0.909	0.715	
	Bt2	1.026	0.033	30.819	0.000	0.899			0.809
	Bt3	0.824	0.034	24.375	0.000	0.796			0.663
	Bt4	0.833	0.035	23.924	0.000	0.788			0.620
Purchase Intention	Pi1	1.000			0.672	0.910	0.892	0.682	
	Pi2	0.980	0.068	14.317	0.000	0.644			0.953
	Pi3	1.347	0.066	20.492	0.000	0.976			0.414
	Pi4	1.320	0.065	20.207	0.000	0.954			0.451

4.3. Discriminant validity

The Fornell-Larcker criterion was used to examine whether the measurement instrument had discriminant validity. According to the Fornell-Larcker criterion, the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) of a factor/construct must be greater than the correlations of that factor with other factors (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Therefore, the discriminant validity of the items in the research model is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Discriminant validity analysis

	CRM	WOM	BT	PI
CRM	0.774			
WOM	0.472	0.914		
BT	0.426	0.771	0.845	
PI	0.428	0.791	0.771	0.826

4.4. Model fit assessment

Structural equation modeling (SEM) was adopted to analyze all research path hypotheses. The fit values obtained from the SEM analysis indicate that the model has a good fit. The analysis results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Model fit index

Fit index	Allowable range	Research model fit
X ²	The smaller the better	8891.779
df	The larger the better	136
X ² /df	≤5	3.827
GFI	≥0.90	0.915
NFI	≥0.90	0.952
RFI	≥0.90	0.941
IFI	≥0.90	0.964
TLI	≥0.90	0.956
CFI	≥0.90	0.964
SRMR	≤0.08	0.071
RMSEA	≤0.08	0.071

4.5. Hypothesis verification

In the process of validating research hypotheses, the R² value is examined first. The R² value indicates how much of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables. Therefore, a high R² value is preferred. The structural model is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. SEM structure model

In this study, the explained variance score (R²) for the effect of customer relationship management (Relationship) and positive word-of-mouth (WOM) on brand trust is 0.60, indicating that the research model has good explanatory power. The explained variance score

(R²) for the effect of positive word-of-mouth (WOM) and brand trust on purchase intention is 0.69, indicating that the research model has good explanatory power. The results of the regression analysis are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. List of regression a nalysis

Dependent variable	Independent variable	Unstandardized regression coefficient	S.E.	C.R.	p	Standardized regression coefficient	R ²
WOM	CRM	0.815	0.098	8.287	0.000	0.474	0.225
BT	CRM	0.130	0.058	2.250	0.024	0.082	0.599
	WOM	0.674	0.038	17.532	0.000	0.732	
PI	WOM	0.359	0.038	9.419	0.000	0.485	0.690
	BT	0.319	0.040	7.952	0.000	0.397	

H₁: Customer relationship management has a significant influence on pozitive WOM

The unstandardized regression coefficient of customer relationship management (CRM) to positive WOM (WOM) is 0.815, reaching a significant level (c.r =8.287, p=0.00); thus, the hypothesis is supported.

H₂: Customer relationship management has a significant influence on brand trus

The unstandardized regression coefficient of customer relationship management (CRM) to brand trust (BT) is 0.13, reaching a significant level (c.r =2.250, p=0.02); thus, the hypothesis is supported.

H₃: Positive WOM has a significant influence on brand trus

The unstandardized regression coefficient of positive WOM (WOM) to brand trust (BT) is 0.674, reaching a significant level (c.r =17.532, p=0.00); thus, the hypothesis is supported.

H₄: Positive WOM has a significant influence on purchase intention

The unstandardized regression coefficient of positive WOM (WOM) to purchase intention (PI) is 0.359, reaching a significant level (c.r =9.419, p=0.00); thus, the hypothesis is supported.

H₅: Brand trust has a significant influence on purchase intention

The unstandardized regression coefficient of brand trust (BT) to purchase intention (PI) is 0.319, reaching a significant level (c.r =7.952, p=0.00); thus, the hypothesis is supported.

4.6. Analysis on mediating effect

After hypothesis testing, mediation effects were examined. The mediation analysis included total, direct, and indirect effects. The results of the analysis are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Analysis of mediating model indirect effects

Effect	Point estimate	Product of coefficients		Bootstrap 5000 times	
		S.E.	p	Bias corrected 95%	
				Lower bound	Upper bound
Standardized total effect CRM→BT	0.429	0.050	0.000	0.328	0.522
Standardized direct effect CRM→BT	0.082	0.044	0.059	-0.003	0.167

Standardized indirect effect CRM→WOM→BT	0.347	0.036	0.000	0.275	0.418
Standardized total effect WOM→PI	0.776	0.026	0.000	0.723	0.823
Standardized direct effect WOM→PI	0.485	0.057	0.000	0.369	0.593
Standardized indirect effect WOM→BT→PI	0.291	0.046	0.000	0.204	0.389

H₆: The mediating effect of positive WOM between customer relationship management (CRM) and brand trust (BT)

The indirect impact of customer relationship management on brand trust through positive WOM is significant ($p < 0,05$). This confidence interval does not include 0 [0.275, 0.418], which means that the total indirect effect and the mediating effect are supported.

H₇: The mediating effect of brand trust (BT) between positive WOM (WOM) and purchase intention (PI)

The indirect impact of positive WOM on purchase intention through brand trust is significant ($p < 0,05$). This confidence interval does not include 0 [0.204, 0.389], which means that the total indirect effect and the mediating effect are supported.

5. Discussions

This study examines the relationships between CRM and positive WOM, brand trust, and purchase intention on OTT TV platforms. The analysis results show that CRM positively influences both positive WOM and brand trust; positive WOM positively influences both brand trust and purchase intention; and brand trust increases purchase intention. Furthermore, positive WOM mediates the relationship between CRM and brand trust, while brand trust mediates the relationship between positive WOM and purchase intention. The findings indicate that consumer attitudes and behaviors on OTT TV platforms are shaped by user-to-user communication, relationship management, and trust.

The first finding of the study is that CRM has a positive effect on positive WOM (Word of Mouth). This finding shows that consumers are more likely to recommend platforms that improve user experience, offer personalized services to customers, and maintain continuous interaction with customers. This finding means that customer experience on OTT TV platforms is not limited to the usage process but also affects users' behavior in recommending the platform to others. This finding is consistent with previous studies showing that user experience increases recommendation intention. Studies, particularly those related to music and digital streaming platforms, have shown that service quality and customer satisfaction increase recommendation intention (Barata & Coelho, 2021).

Another finding of the study is that CRM has a positive effect on brand trust. Within the scope of digital services, elements such as service continuity, customer support, data security, and content quality stand out as important factors for consumers. Accordingly, it can be stated that OTT TV platforms that establish strong relationships with their customers are more successful in building brand trust. This finding is also parallel to previous studies that have shown that brand trust is related to platform quality, interaction, and user experience. In particular, studies

related to digital streaming services highlight personalized experience and user interaction as determinants of brand trust (Akrom, 2025).

Another finding of the study is that positive WOM has a positive effect on brand trust. One of the most important factors in building trust in digital services is users being influenced by the experiences of other consumers. In particular, user comments and recommendations sharing their experiences on online platforms reduce the perception of uncertainty for potential users. This finding is consistent with previous studies that have shown the effect of positive WOM on trust (Luthfi et al., 2025; Tafolli et al., 2025; Tohari et al., 2025).

Another finding of the study is that positive WOM has a positive effect on purchase intention. This means that positive experiences with OTT TV platforms increase intentions to subscribe. Today, consumers view user reviews from those who have previously experienced a product as a more reliable source of information than advertisements. Therefore, users' social media posts and comments about the product play a significant role in their purchasing decisions. The findings are consistent with previous studies showing that positive WOM is a determining factor in purchase intention (Gupta, 2023; Tjipto & Keni, 2025).

Another finding of the study is that brand trust has a positive effect on purchase intention. This means that users are more likely to subscribe to OTT TV platforms they trust. Considering the subscription-based nature of OTT TV platforms, the importance of trust for user retention becomes evident. This finding is consistent with previous studies showing that brand trust has an effect on purchase intention (Wu & Huang, 2023).

Another finding of the study is that positive WOM plays a mediating role in the relationship between CRM and brand trust. This finding shows that positive communication created among users by CRM strengthens brand trust. In other words, CRM applications encourage customers to share their positive experiences with the platform, and as a result, trust in the brand increases. This finding parallels previous studies that have shown that inter-user communication plays a strategic role in building trust on digital platforms (Akrom, 2025).

Another finding is that brand trust plays a mediating role in the relationship between positive WOM and purchase intention. This finding suggests that positive recommendations build trust in the brand before directly forming a purchase intention, and this trust then leads to that intention. Therefore, for positive reviews of platforms to be effective, the platform needs to have a trustworthy brand image. This finding parallels previous studies that have shown brand trust to be a significant psychological element in digital consumer behavior (Tjipto & Keni, 2025).

6. Conclusions

The study's findings indicate that consumer attitudes and behaviors towards OTT TV platforms depend not only on price and content quality, but also on relational factors such as trust, user experience, inter-user communication, and relationship management. In highly competitive market conditions, the sustainable success of OTT TV platforms depends on building their strategies on trust and establishing long-term relationships with their customers.

6.1. Theoretical implications

This study makes significant contributions to the literature on digital platforms. Its primary contribution lies in addressing the variables within a single model framework and explaining

the relationships between these variables holistically. Furthermore, it reveals the relational and psychological mechanisms that explain digital consumer behavior, facilitating a better understanding of them. It also makes a significant contribution to the literature by highlighting the role of trust in subscription-based services such as OTT TV. In addition, it reveals the role of communication between users in the success of digital platforms.

6.2. Limitations

This study has some limitations. The primary limitation is that the research data was collected from a limited number of participants in a limited region. This may limit the generalizability of the research findings. Considering that digital platform usage habits can be influenced by regional, economic, and demographic differences, it is believed that studies with different sample sizes could yield more comprehensive results.

The use of convenience sampling in the study is also a significant limitation. Since the participants were selected through face-to-face surveys on Sakarya's busiest street and based on accessibility criteria, it cannot be said that the sample fully represents the population. Therefore, there is a possibility of bias stemming from the sampling method.

In addition, data were collected over a single time period using a cross-sectional research design. While this allows for the identification of relationships between variables, it limits the precise establishment of causal relationships. Using longitudinal research designs in future studies may yield more powerful results in examining how relationships between variables change over time. Another limitation of the study is that the data was collected using the self-report method. Participants may have responded based on their social desirability tendencies or personal perceptions. This situation can lead to bias in measurements.

6.3. Recommendations

Based on the research findings, it is recommended that OTT TV platforms place greater emphasis on customer relationship management practices. Personalized content recommendations that improve user experience, prompt customer support, and effective feedback mechanisms can increase user satisfaction. Furthermore, platforms developing social media and digital community strategies that encourage users to share their positive experiences can contribute to the creation of positive WOM.

OTT TV platforms need to pay more attention to trust-building practices. Factors valued by consumers, such as openness, transparency, service continuity, and data security in subscription processes, will build brand trust. To increase the generalizability of the models, similar models can be tested on different platform types, different cultural samples, and different age groups in future studies. Furthermore, variables such as perceived value, brand loyalty, user satisfaction, and platform engagement can be added to the model to obtain comprehensive results.

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